

Inclusive Education as A Matter of Education for All

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Abstract

The studies focused on multicultural education and multi-religion. It finds some strategies like unity in diversity, integrating cultural diversity in the curriculum relevant to culture and its senses towards enlightening the things of the pupil value the things, habits for life and their work and inculcation of the spirit and visions, the presence of nobility relevant to the field of education shows the wider scope on social, political and personal interest. The combination of two or more cultures integrating on the society, community and societal background for the occupying of the cultural education in the society. The origin of multicultural education centralized is positively using cultural diversity in the totality of learning.

The main objectives of multicultural education is to enlighten the levels of basic skills, cultural settings, to think critically and to develop the habit of tolerance and patience in the student and community. It goes through with a different levels of activities like athletic program, project, club activities etc.. it also incorporating with the student voice, dialogic enquiry establishing co-operative learning, to develop teacher pupil interactions to the field of curriculum on the basis of multicultural education and multi religion.

Keywords: Education, Culture, Cultural Diversity, Multicultural Education, Co-Operative Learning

Introduction

Concept of Introduction

Three historic developments in the 199's powered ways for the emergence of the concept of inclusion. First, the movement on "Education for all (EFA)" which originated from the international conference jointly organized by the world Bank, UNESCO and UNICEF in Jomtein. Thailand in 1990 and reminded Governments on the need to treat Education of disadvantaged section in the jomete in declaration, the real thrust for inclusion emerged at the international conference organized by UNESCO in Salamanca, Spain in collaboration with the government of Spain in 1994. which brought together more than 300 participants of the conference emphasized the need for importing enabling schools where every child including children with special needs has a place to acquire leaeaning experience.

The actual statement made at the conference conveys the true sprit of "Schools for All" concept which supports not to look at the difference between children but similarities in order to consider that children but similarities in order to consider that children is a special child and a better school system can address the educational requirements of children with specific learning difficulties.

The third historical development was the later (2000) which stressed the need for time bound action in such a way that education for all children is achieved by the year 2015.

The attempt to define "what is all" In the EFA created a need to reach out to children who did not have access to formal education. Through the population of "out of school" children included various categories such as children of migrant Workers, orphans, children with below poverty line (BPL) families, children with disabilities etc. The term "inclusion" is referred often in the case of disability. There is a vivid reason why the professionals stated linking inclusion with disabilities.

The earlier approaches to educate children with disabilities mostly adopted exclusive strategies which generally embraced a theory that children with disabilities require facilities. Different from that of non disabled children and therefore exclusive approach remained the most accepted model to educate children with disabilities.

Attempts to identify similarities between children with disabilities and non disabled children in the hearing process brought in a paradigm shift in educational approaches too.

Researches on "multi-sensory" approaches in hearing learning revealed that lack of ability in one faculty does not totally hamper started

looking at "similarities" Between disabled children and non-disabled children. Through it was not possible to observe perfect similarities more "like" than "unlike" characteristics paved ways for brining children with disabilities to general schools and a result the terminologies "integration" and "mainstreaming" emerged.

The integrated education model believed in providing education to children with disabilities in general education system could be improved to address specific hearing needs of children with disabilities.

The approach of "effective schools" emerged in the 1990's which stressed the need to prepare Teachers. Who acquire skills to address the diverse needs of children in the classroom without labeling their' as children with disabilities.

In order to provide effective education and respond to pupil diversity, there would sometimes be a need to implement particular teaching Approaches with specific children at various times.

The teaching education resource pack of UNESCO (1995) underlined the need to treat every child in the classroom as a special child this broad paradigm shift in the learning process. Changed the entire approach to inclusion and as a Result Children with disabilities were referred to as "children" with "special needs" meaning that there are non-disabled children too in the learning system who may require special attention of teachers booth and ainscow (1998) who did extensive work on inclusive education state.

Characteristics of Inclusive Education

1. Children with disabilities are enrolled in local general schools.
2. Enrolment of children with disabilities mandatory as a result of the campaign for education for all (EFA) children that includes disabled children too.
3. All categories of children with disabilities and all levels are enrolled in schools.
4. All general classroom teachers in the schools are oriented to the educational needs of children with disabilities.
5. A special teacher is appointed for a block or for a Chester of schools and pay visits to schools based on the needs of disabled children.
6. There is a cluster level resource centre where all assistive and assessment devices are available.
7. Frequent in-service programmers are organized to improve the skill of general classroom teachers in teaching children with disabilities.
8. Children with disabilities are sometimes brought to the resource centre if necessary.
9. Children with disabilities are enrolled even if special teachers are not available.

"Education contributes to an individual's journey to-words self-reliance and independence. Schools and instruction must be designed and organized to meet the varying needs of individual learners.

Special education is specialized instruction and supplementary aids and services provided to students with disabilities who need specialized instruction. Some students (labeled as receiving special education or not) may need or want to spend

some of their time learning in a quieter place with fewer people or with additional help from others.

Types of Children Requiring Special Education or Inclusion

1. Attention deficit disorder.
2. Deaf and hearing impaired.
3. Gifted
4. Learning disabilities.
5. Physically challenged
6. Blind and visual challenged.
7. Developments disability.

Meaning and Definition of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education means,
Valuing all students and staff equally

1. Increasing the participation of students in and reducing their exclusion from the cultures, policies and practices in schools so that they respond to the diversity of students in the locality.
2. Reducing barriers to learning and participation for all students not only those with impairments educational needs

According to Dr. Melissa Hesston

When good inclusion is in place the child who needs the inclusion doesn't stand out the inclusive curriculum includes strong parental involvement students making choice and a lot of hands on and heads on involvement.

According to Dr. Kathy East

Inclusive education means teachers working with students in a context that is suitable to a diverse population of students. It's difficult to get teachers to do this.

According to Dr. Susan

Inclusion is based on the belief that people or adults work in inclusive communities work with people of different races, religions, aspirations disabilities, in the same vein , children of all ages should learn and grow in environments that resemble the environments that they will eventually work in,

National Concerns and Education.

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Teaching Subject Areas

Some methods of teaching useful for children with disabilities are listed as follows.

Play-Way Method of Teaching

In this method the child is not kept in the classroom as a bookish learner. The child is introduced to the lesson through a no. of play activities the teacher introduced specific concepts.

Children who are learning through play-way method experience a sense of discovery.

Providing Concrete Experiences

While learning pass through in 3 developmental stages, firstly they need concrete experiences secondly they can learn through pictorial ideas and thirdly the development through concrete experiences.

Teacher Assisted Peer Group Learning

Peer group learning contributes to effective learning in the case of non disabled children.

For adopting peer-group learning a lot of preparation on the part of the teacher is needed activities for peer group learning strategies for intervention etc. As to be thoroughly planned by the teacher.

Teaching in A Step by Step Way

Due to the loss of a specific family children with disabilities lose the sequence of learning experiences. Teaching in a step by step sequence becomes vital for children with disabilities. They are forced by the absence of the senses when teaching is done in a step system.

Modifying Methods of Teaching to List the Learning Styles of Disabled Children

The teacher should ascertain whether the child is a visual learner or an auditory learner or a tactile learner for designing proper intuitional strategies though Classification of this kind is imperative in the general classroom too, its application with disabilities is of paramount importance because these children exhibit different skills at different levels.

Criterion Based Teaching as well as Execution Techniques

Usually evaluation in a regular classroom is norm based. The teacher evaluates a child on the basis of quantitative scores. However this type of evaluation may not be proper for all activities in the case of children with disabilities science disabled children have to learn curricular as well as pulse curricular

Activities. In criterion based evaluation there is no pressure of comparative performance and the child learns in a natural way.

Learning through Field Trips and Hands on Experience

Since children with disability experience reduction in the range and variety of experiences in many aspects, they need to be compensated by alternative modes of information field trips are such alternative experiences which mostly contribute to the proper concept development of these children.

Use of Supplementary Teaching Aids and Appliances for Developing Appropriate Concepts

Sometimes a concept thought by the teachers using the normal mode of information may not be appropriate for the child with disability to understand. Therefore it is essential to use additional teacher aids which may provide the needed concept development in the child.

Individualized Educational Programmes

For mentally retarded children their needs and abilities must be assessed and appropriate instructional strategies must be designed and addressed based on their strengths and needs. When the above aspects are addressed by the regular classroom teacher teaching of any subject would become easier for the disabled child.

When Does Inclusion of all Children Work Best

Inclusion works best when there is a fundamental change in the approach of classroom management all children including with the disability can get all children including with the disability effective education when the following key concepts are taken care of in general classroom and in this context. The classroom teacher plays a key role.

1. Inclusion is education recognizes the fact that every child is special in one way or the other the teacher with such an approach realizes that each child has learning ability at different levels. Though classroom instruction in general is made uniform in respect of the intellectual abilities of the children a true teacher plays attention to the individual capabilities of the children a true teacher plays attention to individual capabilities of the children. In such a classroom in division of all children take place and they are not categorized on the basis of color creed, intellect, disability etc.,
2. Teacher with such an approach understands and capitalizes the collective strength of the classroom. He/she will never hesitate to take help from students rather he/she would use the abilities of the students for constructive purposes. Such a teacher realize that students both disabled and non-disabled can also contribute to problem solving situation in the classroom.
3. A true teacher who believes in inclusion facilitates peer to peer learning in nature the teacher is expected to promote peer group. Learning as a vehicle to overcome the students inhibitions and would gradually make the entire classroom non-threatening. A properly guided peer-group learning activity would make learning faster too. A child with any type of disadvantage will not experience discrimination.
4. In an effective classroom, the teacher makes optimum utilization of the available teaching aids and assistive devices. Instead of demanding for more and more teaching aids a creative teacher make use of the environment itself to develop. Appropriate concepts instead of insisting too much on theoretical learning. The teacher will encourage learning by doing and interactive learning approaches to make as optimum use of the teaching aids as well as the environment for effective learning. When the teacher encourages learning by doing disadvantaged children who require concrete experience are benefited much.
5. A true teacher is always conscious of the fact and the students are human beings and not learning machines, this approach make the teacher to set realistic goals for the students. Often the ordinary teacher thinks that his/her subject is the only important subject and loads the students with a

lot of home work and alignments. Likewise other teacher too do the same thing and as a Result those unable to complete the home work this feeling of failure lower the Self esteem of the child. Teacher should always realize the fact that the students have their limit and therefore. Set learning objectives and provide work which are realistic as children with disadvantages.

6. A true teacher will adopt multi sensory approach in learning. The learning Should be experimental to the students and hence an effective teacher will make the class room itself conductive place for learning he/she will motivate each and every students of the class to involve in active learning and will be flexible so the children feel free in the classroom he/she will identify the learning preference visual auditory or tactile of the students and facilitate learning through small and groups. Even the physical students of the classroom may be changed by the teacher to emerge effective learning. This multisensory approach is not only useful for children with disabilities but for other children too who experiences learning problem.
7. An effective teacher supervises the learning activities of the students regularly. He/she will try not to find fault with the work of students but helps in rectifying their mistake through constructive criticism. This positive approach provides better learning environment to children with disabilities and other disadvantaged groups. As is evident from the previous description inclusion emphasizes the importance of individual and revealing his/her potential in the learning process.

Should We Support Inclusive Education?

Disabled children have an equal right, to membership of the same groups as Everybody also segregated education restricts that right and limits for self-fulfillment people with disabilities or learning difficulties do not need to be Separated or protected.

Inclusive education is a human rights issue many more children could be included in the mainstream with benefits to everyone. Disabled adults. Describing them as special school survivors are demanding an end to segregated education.

The Process of Inclusion can be Supported now by:

1. A change in attitudes.
2. Putting into practice a started commitment to the principles of inclusive education and communities.
3. Reducing not increasing the proportion selected out for special school education.
4. Re-allocating from the segregated sector the extensive resources (money, equipment etc. and the expertise (teaching and non-teaching) to the mainstream.
5. Adapting initial and in-service training of teachers supporting head teachers and governor's in these changes.
6. Listening to disabled peoples views on their experiences of special school education.
7. Understanding that the greatest, barriers to inclusion are caused by society not by particular medical impairments.

Barriers of Inclusive Education

Many factors enter into creating inclusive classrooms in which children with disabilities learn along with typical peers. Any one of these failures or lack of any, can effect inclusion and the quality of a students education,

Major barriers associated with inclusive educator are,

Expense

Funding is the major constraint to the practice of inclusion. Teaching student's with disabilities in general education classrooms taken specialists and additional staff to support students needs. Coordinating services and offering individual supports to children requires additional money that many schools do not have

Miss-Information

Some of the greatest barrier associated with inclusion in education is negative attitudes, as with society in general these attitudes and stereo types are often caused by lack of knowledge and understanding the attitudes and abilities of general education teachers and Para educators in particular can be major limitations in inclusive education, training teachers and Para educators to understand and work with children with disabilities is often in advance or it may be fragmented and uncoordinated.

Accessibility

Obviously, a student with disability cannot learn in a inclusive class room let alone the school building. Some schools are still inaccessible to students in wheelchairs or to those other mobility aides. A student with cerebral palsy, for instance may not have the ability to group and turn traditional Classroom must be able to accommodate a students associate technology devices, as well as other furniture must individual needs.

Educational Modifications

Just as the environment must he accessible to students with disabilities, the curriculum must facilitate inclusive education too, general education must willing to work with inclusion specialists to make modifications and accommodations in both teaching methods and classroom and home work assignments.

Co-operation

One of the final barriers associated with inclusion education is a lack of communication among administrators, teachers, specialists, staff parents and students open communication and co-coordinated planning between general education teachers and special education staff are essential for inclusion to work. Time is needed for teachers and specialists to meet and create well constructed plans to identify and implement modifications accommodations and specific goals for individual students. Collaboration must also exist among teachers.

Class Room Activities to Overcome Attitudinal Barriers

The following activities help in overcoming attitudinal barriers and also facilitate better inclusion of children with disabilities in the classroom.

Learning Plus Curricular Activities by Non Disabled Children

Children with disabilities have to master plus curricular activities for their effective inclusion however orientation of these to non disabled children

would facilitate better inclusion for children with disabilities.

Modification of Curricular Content and Transactional Strategies to Inclusion

In inclusive settings there is no need to change the entire curriculum when children with visual impairment hearing impairment and locomotors disability are enrolled.

Curricular Adaptations

Adaptations may be in terms of methods of presentation display, content etc. To enhance the learning experiences of these children. This approach not only helps children with disabilities but also helps the teacher to assist children who have learning problems.

Concept Development

Concept development is fundamental in the education of children with disabilities particularly for those who are cognitively impaired such as mentally retarded children and those with sensory impairment including visually impaired children and hearing impaired children these have to be consciously developed in children with disabilities.

In addition to suggesting curriculum in teacher education courses the joint committee also put forth several recommendations for the implementation of inclusive curriculum in teacher preparation and also for regulating such human resource development programmes. The salient recommendations are as follows;

1. Availability of a resource room consisting of base assistive devices be made desirable in general teacher in general teacher education institutions for according recognition by NCTE this may also be made as a part of the language laboratory and the audio-visual laboratory which are mandatory in general prepared institutions.
2. The RCI inspection team for teacher education causes may include a nominee from the NCTE.
3. The joint committee was of the view that the existing norms of teacher preparation causes of RCI by the RCI are in conformation with the norms of the general teacher education causes approved by the NCTE.
4. The joint committee recommended that the B.Ed, general education and Bed. special education may be considered equivalent for career opportunities salary, promotions etc.
5. RCI and NCTE may appoint expert committees for preparing course materials for the capacities building programmes of general teacher educators to give knowledge in special education

This joint work of NCTE and RCI is just a beginning and there needs to be a strong collaboration between the two regulatory bodies for the betterment of special education teacher preparation there by addressing human resources needs to see the vast majority of unreached children with disabilities in India.

Conclusion

1. Inclusive education is one of the most dominant issues in right to education for all
2. It is not unproblematic, both conceptually and practically.
3. In recent years the concept of inclusive education has been broadened to encompass not only

students with disabilities but also all students who may be disadvantaged.

4. Autocracy inclusive education revolves around Main Arguments

1. Inclusive education is a basic human right.
2. In test education program for students with disabilities the focus must be shift from the individuals impairments to social context, a key feature of which should be a variety education system Dedicated to providing quality education for all students.
3. Since there is no clear demarcation between the characteristics of students with and without disabilities and there is no support for the contention that specific categories of students learn differently separate provision for such students cannot be justified.
4. The characterization purpose and from inclusive education reflect the relationship among the social political economic cultural and historical contents real are present at any one time in a particular country and or local authority.
5. The united nations and its agency UNESCO have played a significant role in promoting inclusive education.
6. Inclusive education goes for beyond the physical placement of children with disabilities in general classroom but requires nothing less than transformer regular education by promoting school classroom culture structures and practices that accumulate to diversity.

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